

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Analysis of Toddler Consumption Patterns in the SEHATI CSR Program of PT Pertamina Patra Niaga Integrated Terminal Makassar

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Abstract

Consumption patterns are a person's eating habits that include the type and frequency of food. During infancy, balanced nutritional intake is essential for growth and development. Poor food intake can lead to decreased health status and nutritional problems in toddlers. This study aims to describe the consumption patterns of toddlers in the Tabaringan Community Health Center, Ujung Tanah District, who participated in the SEHATI CSR program of PT Pertamina Patra Niaga Integrated Terminal Makassar. This type of research is descriptive using quantitative data with a sample of 21 people. Data were collected by conducting interviews using a food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) form. This study used univariate analysis. The results obtained in this study are the types of food with the highest consumption frequency of staple foods, namely rice, animal side dishes are quail eggs, vegetable side dishes are tempeh and tofu, vegetables are kale and fruits are bananas. Toddlers are expected to consume a variety of foods every day and require the role of parents in serving a variety of foods with different processing methods and the use of food ingredients that are adjusted to food availability and prices.

Keywords: Consumption Patterns; Toddlers; Stunting; Food Frequency

1. Introduction

Toddlers are children aged 0-5 years. The toddler period is a crucial period in human growth and development due to its rapid rate (Akbar et al., 2020). Toddlers aged 0-59 months are characterized by rapid growth and development, accompanied by changes that require higher levels of high-quality nutrients. However, toddlers are a vulnerable group and susceptible to nutritional disorders due to a lack of adequate nutrition. Food consumption plays a crucial role in a child's physical and intellectual growth, thus significantly impacting their nutritional status, contributing to their physical and intellectual growth. The term "toddler" is commonly used for children up to 5 years old. Children aged 1 to 3 years are referred to as toddlers, and those aged 3 to 5 years are referred to as preschoolers. Toddlers are still fully dependent on their parents for all their activities. During the toddler period, the process of child growth is a very important stage, during this period it is determining whether the child's growth will be better in the following period. The golden age is another name for this period and will never be repeated again. (Sutomo & Anggraini, 2010).

One of the periods or ages vulnerable to nutritional problems is toddlerhood. If children's growth and development do not occur optimally at this age, they will fail to become quality human resources. Nutrient intake is essential for the body to perform its functions such as producing energy, building and maintaining tissue (Wijayanti and Nindya, 2017). Child nutrition problems are broadly the result of an imbalance between nutrient intake and output (nutritional imbalance), that is, intake exceeding output or vice versa. Furthermore, errors in food selection are common. The consequences of this dependency are chronic disease, overweight or underweight (Arisman, 2014).

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Based on the results of the basic health research (riskesdas) of the Ministry of Health in 2018, 17.7% of 5-year-old infants (toddlers) still experience problems with their nutritional status. This figure consists of toddlers who experience malnutrition by 3.9%, and suffering from malnutrition by 13.8%. The number of toddlers with malnutrition and malnutrition in Indonesia according to the results of nutritional status monitoring in 2015, toddlers aged 0-59 months who experience malnutrition by 3.9% and malnutrition by 14.9%, experienced a slight decrease in 2016, toddlers aged 0-59 months who experience malnutrition by 3.4% and malnutrition by 14.4%, (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2017).

A factor influencing the nutritional status of toddlers is the feeding patterns provided by the toddler's mother. Feeding patterns are a person's behavior that can influence nutritional status. Eating patterns can provide an overview of nutritional intake, including the type, amount, and schedule in fulfilling nutrition (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2014). Malnutrition is a condition where the body weight for age (BW/A) is not appropriate for the age. Malnutrition is vulnerable to occur in toddlers aged 2-5 years because toddlers have adopted a diet similar to family meals and begin to have high levels of physical activity. Malnutrition during infancy is related to brain development, so it can affect a child's intelligence and impact the formation of the quality of human resources in the future.

The background description above became a consideration for researchers to examine the consumption patterns of toddlers who participated in the SEHATI CSR program of PT Pertamina Patra Niaga Integrated Terminal Makassar in the working area of the Tabaringan Health Center, Ujung Tanah District, Makassar City.

2. Methods

The study was conducted using descriptive research using quantitative data. It was conducted in June with the subjects being toddlers who were beneficiaries of the SEHATI CSR Program of PT Pertamina Patra Niaga Integrated Terminal Makassar in the Tabaringan Community Health Center working area of Ujung Tanah District. The research sample used a total population of 21 respondents. Data were collected using a food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) form which was then analyzed univariately.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Consumption Patterns

3.1.1. Staple Foods

Table 1 Distribution of Consumption Patterns by Staple Foods.

Food Ingredients	Eating Frequency					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
Rice	21	0	0	0	0	0
Potato	0	7	0	3	7	4
Noodeles	0	0	3	7	8	3
Sweet Potatoes	0	0		4	7	10

Source: Primary Data 2025

Table 1 shows that toddlers most frequently consume rice as a staple food, three times a day. This means that at each main meal (breakfast, lunch, and dinner), respondents definitely consume rice as a source of carbohydrates.

3.1.2. Animal Side Dishes

Table 2 Distribution of Animal Side Dish Consumption Patterns

Food Ingredients	Eating Frequency					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
Beef	0	0	5	8	8	0
Chicken	0	0	7	8	6	0
Duck	0	0	0	0	3	18
Quail Eggs	0	21	0	0	0	0
Roast Chicken Eggs	0	0	0	10	4	7
Scaded Mackerel	0	0	7	3	11	0
Milkfish	0	0	10	5	6	0
Anchovies	0	0	5	8	7	0

Source: Primary Data 2025

Table 2 shows the consumption of animal side dishes. Quail eggs are the most frequently consumed by toddlers, with a frequency of once per day.

3.1.3. Vegetable Side Dishes

Table 3 Distribution of Vegetable Side Dish Consumption Patterns

Food Ingredients	Eating Frequency					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
Green beans	0	0	0	3	9	13
Red beans	0	0	0	0	0	21
Tempe	0	13	0	0	6	0
Tahu	0	10	4	0	0	7
Peanuts	0	0	0	0	0	21
Sunflower seeds	0	0	0	0	0	21

Source: Primary Data 2025

Table 3 shows that toddlers most frequently consume tempe and tofu once a day.

3.1.4. Vegetables and Fruit

Table 4 Distribution of Vegetable Consumption Patterns

Food Ingredients	Eating Frequency					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
Broccoli	0	0	0	0	0	21
Cassava leaves	0	0	0	4	8	9
Yellow corn	0	2	3	3	9	4
Kankung	0	10	3	0	6	2
Spinach	0	8	3	0	2	6

Long beans	0	7	0	4	8	2
Cabbage	0	0	9	6	3	3
Chayote	0	0	0	5	10	6
Bean sprouts	0	0	5	6	2	8
Carrots	0	0	11	6	2	2
Tomatoes	0	0	5	8	2	6

Source: Primary Data 2025

Table 4 shows that water spinach is the most commonly consumed vegetable, once per daily. Additionally, carrots are vegetables consumed 3-6 times per week. There are vegetables that toddlers haven't consumed in the past month, such as broccoli.

Table 5 Distribution of Fruit Consumption Patterns

Food Ingredients	Eating Frequency					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
Bananas	0	0	15	2	4	0
Avocados	0	0	0	3	15	3
Apples	0	0	5	6	10	0
Durian	0	0	0	0	0	21
Guava	0	0	0	0	5	16
Oranges	0	0	5	5	11	0
Mango	0	0	5	8	8	0
Papaya	0	0	6	2	5	8
Lansat	0	0	0	0	0	21
Salak	0	0	0	0	0	21
Rembutan	0	0	0	0	0	21
Watermelon	0	0	8	5	8	0

Source: Primary Data 2025

Table 5 shows that in the past month, toddlers most frequently They consume fruit 3-6 times per week, especially bananas. The fruits that respondents do not consume most often include durian, lansat, salak, and rambutan..

4. Conclusion

The conclusion of this study is that the food choices consumed by toddlers receiving Sehati Pertamina in the Tabaringan Community Health Center area are not yet diverse, and not all food items have been consumed in the past month. The recommendation from this study is to provide educational activities for mothers of toddlers regarding diverse and nutritious foods for children, as well as providing education on how to prepare diverse and nutritious foods.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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